

Memory Effects During Co-Deposition of Binary Alloys

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The possibility of memory effects during the co-deposition of binary alloy with simultaneous phase separation is studied on the atomistic scale by the Stochastic Kinetic Mean-Field method. At first, the morphology map is found for the asymptotic structures obtained under various compositions of deposition flux and various deposition rates, starting from random alloy at the initial atomic plane. Such a map consists of “single-phase” and “two-phase” regions. At that, a new way of morphology quantification is suggested. The best candidates for keeping memory about the initial morphology (if it is not a random alloy anymore) are the systems from the “two-phase region”. They indeed demonstrate the memory effects at least in mean-field modeling.

Keywords: co-deposition, decomposition, pattern, morphology quantification, diffusion, kinetic mean-field method.

Pattern formation during directional eutectic crystallization from the liquid phase and co-deposition from the vapor phase is not only a very interesting example of self-organization in open systems under external fluxes and gradients¹⁻⁵ but as well a new perspective way to produce and optimize the new multiphase materials or even metamaterials for applications in photonics, energy storage, and conversion⁶⁻¹².

In the past decades, different simulation approaches have been proposed to contribute to the understanding of the film formation during different elaboration techniques. In particular, special attention has been paid to pattern formation during film deposition. More globally, the morphological transition during separation kinetics in alloy is one of the most important research topics for pattern formation in materials science and physics.

At mesoscale the phase-field method (PFM) appears as a well-established technique for solving interfacial problems with diffuse interfaces¹³. In particular, this method has been applied to study a morphological evolution during spinodal decomposition of a binary alloy thin film elastically constrained by a substrate¹⁴. It was shown that without coherency strain, the compositional fluctuation simultaneously occurs in the whole film from the initial stage of the spinodal decomposition and form labyrinth-type structure. When the coherency strain is introduced, the phase separation follows the mechanism of surface-directed spinodal. It was also underlined that with increasing of the elastic strain a rod-like structure can be formed. Recently, the PFM has been applied to study the effects of deposition rate, dissimilar bulk and surface kinetics, phase fraction, and dissimilar elastic response on the resulting microstructure in nanocomposite thin-films during simulated physical vapor deposition¹⁵. The gradual change in the decomposition behavior with increasing distance from the coating surface has been revealed by Atom Probe Tomography (APT) analyses in the TiAlN/CrN multilayer coating¹⁶.

Despite years of activity in this direction, we still have several unsolved important problems concerning the prediction of morphology for liquid-solid and vapor-solid transformations

under external gradients and fluxes:

A. The morphology of the obtained patterns depends on the external parameters (pulling velocity and temperature gradient in eutectic crystallization by micro-pulling-down method, deposition rate, and vapor composition in co-deposition method). First of all, it depends strongly on the composition of liquid or vapor phases. For example, compositions close to equiatomic prefer lamellar or labyrinth structures. Compositions closer to one of the constituents of the eutectic couple, prefer rod-like morphology. There exist also some combined morphologies - for example, broken lamellae or lamellae with some rods. Yet, the quantification of morphology remains a problem. Recent application of principal component analysis (PCA) to the quantification of morphology¹⁷⁻¹⁹ shows a possible way to “expand” and compare morphologies within the data science approach. Yet, we still need some simple method to distinguish automatically the main structures.

B. In closed systems, the equilibrium state is a true final state, which does not depend on the initial state because it is determined by the extremum of the corresponding thermodynamic function (maximum of entropy for isolated systems, minimum of Helmholtz free energy for systems in homogeneous thermal bath with fixed temperature and volume, minimum of Gibbs free energy for systems in homogeneous thermal bath with fixed temperature and pressure). Therefore, reaching the true equilibrium by the closed system should mean that the initial state is forgotten. Yet, even for closed systems the memory effects (hysteresis) of long-living metastable states (instead of finally equilibrium) can exist.

In the case of open systems in inhomogeneous external conditions (for example, different chemical potentials or temperature at different boundaries) the equilibrium is inconsistent with boundary conditions and therefore, impossible. Instead of equilibrium with zero fluxes, such systems usually tend to steady-state with constant fluxes. In this case, the determinism of the final state (steady-state) may become questionable. Authors of^{20,21} state that the initial conditions of crystallization from the vapor phase are fully forgotten but they checked

this only for the characteristic separation length - they did not check if the initial topology is also forgotten as well. Even if so, we still should answer - how fast is memory being lost?

In this Letter we treat the different morphologies of the open system which can appear during co-deposition process, in its steady state, as the “phases”. For example, one of the possible “phases” is a “rod-like” morphology meaning an array of isolated spots in each lateral 2D cross-section - often with honeycomb symmetry (Fig. 1a). Three other possible morphologies - “lamellar” (parallel lamellae), “zigzag” and “labyrinth”, are locally similar to each other (locally parallel lamellae) and in the present paper are treated as the same “morphological phase” (Fig. 1b-d), alternative to rod-like phase. On the other hand, in many cases, the mixed morphology is observed, which corresponds to a “two-phase mixture” of two “basic morphologies” - for example, “rods and labyrinth” (Fig. 1e). So, at first, we try to construct the “phase diagram” of morphologies (obtained from initially random first layer) and find the “single-phase” regions and “two-phase” region at the plane “concentration-deposition rate”. We expect that the two-phase region may correspond to ambiguous asymptotic steady states which depend on initial conditions, contrary to single-phase regions. In other words, the initial morphology should be forgotten fast within “single-phase regions”, but may continue to affect even the asymptotic steady-state within “two-phase region” - that is our main hypothesis.

To model the morphology evolution at the atomic scale during vapor co-deposition the Stochastic Kinetic Mean-field (SKMF) method²² has been applied.

To describe the dependence of morphology on external and on initial conditions, it is necessary to quantify the morphology. We introduce and discuss two different morphological parameters. First parameter P_1 ($0 < P_1 < 1$) quantifies the asymmetry of the pattern within the 2D-cross-section. This parameter is high for lamellar pattern and low for rod-like and labyrinth morphology. One more parameter P_2 quantifies the cluster analysis and in some sense is similar to the fractal dimension: $P_2 = \frac{d \ln(N(h))}{d \ln(h)}$, where $N(h)$ is a mean number of clusters of the minority phase ALPHA within the arbitrarily chosen square $h \cdot h$ ($0 < P_2 < \text{about } 2$). This parameter is high for rods (close to 2), medium for labyrinth (from about 1.5 to about 1), and low for lamellar (close to 1). Thus, the measurement of two parameters P_1 and P_2 makes it possible to distinguish at least three morphologies during co-deposition - rod-like, lamellar, and labyrinth. Yet, to simplify the problem, here we treat lamellar and labyrinth morphologies (as well as zigzags) as the same morphological phase.

We demonstrate the examples of simulations for various ratios of deposition rate and diffusion rate within the surface layer. Note that in our SKMF model, the bulk diffusion is treated as totally frozen. Therefore, we do not study here any competition between “vertical” and “lateral” and random concentration modulations: all modulations are “vertical” in our simulations. We demonstrate several examples of memory loss (which is a typical way of understanding), but also some examples of memory keeping with respect to the topology of the patterns.

Finally, the morphology map is constructed and memory effect is checked for the intermediate range of flux compositions (in other terms - possibility of morphological hysteresis).

A co-deposition of a binary alloy of fixed composition C (fraction of atoms A in the deposition flux) with positive mixing energy in binary system AB with fcc crystal structure is simulated. The FCC binary system was deposited on the FCC-substrate with orientations (001) and (111). In all simulations only the nearest neighbors interactions have been considered. The mixing energy E_{mix} was varied from $0.5 k_B T$ to $5 k_B T$. Due to the positive value of the mixing energy, which leads to the separation dynamics, B-clusters are formed just after deposition, as long as surface atoms keep mobility during deposition. The time at which the atoms enhanced “mobility”, within the surface layer of nanometric thickness δ with surface diffusion coefficient D under deposition with velocity V_{dep} is about δ/V_{dep} . During this time the two sorts of atoms can be separated at the distance about $\lambda_{diff} = \sqrt{D \cdot \delta/V_{dep}}$.

One more important characteristic length $\lambda_{capillary} = \frac{\gamma\Omega}{k_B T}$ can be determined by the Gibbs-Thomson effect. So, the nondimensional parameter x^* has been introduced as a ratio of these two length scales:

$$x^* = \frac{\lambda_{capillary}}{\lambda_{diff}} = \frac{\gamma\Omega}{k_B T} \sqrt{\frac{V_{dep}}{D \cdot \delta}} \sim \frac{\gamma\Omega}{k_B T a} \sqrt{\frac{\tau_{surface\ jump}}{\tau_{layer\ deposition}}} \quad (1)$$

where a is an interatomic distance within the surface layer. It can be seen that x^* can be also related to the ration between times, $\tau_{surface\ jump}$, for diffusion jump within the surface layer and the time of single atomic layer deposition, $\tau_{layer\ deposition}$. Usually, the case $x^* \ll 1$ is treated^{20,21}. In this work, the high deposition rates are considered when the characteristic sizes of rods or lamellae may belong to the nanometer scale.

Imagine now (rather artificially) that the co-deposition proceeds layer-by-layer: at first the new atomic layer is deposited completely and only after this, we “switch on” the surface diffusion for some fixed number M of time steps. The diffusion operates by exchange mechanism within non-linear “2.5-D” version of the recent development of stochastic kinetic mean-field model SKMF²²⁻²⁶. (This model was, in its turn, the development of a quasi-one-dimensional KMF model²⁷⁻²⁹). The interatomic exchanges are only permitted in this new plane but the interaction energies are taken into account for nearest neighbors within this plane and also just below this plane. Number M of time steps for surface diffusion before deposition of the new atomic layer, at fixed time step dt , is, evidently, inversely proportional to the deposition rate. Mathematically, as in all kinetic mean-field models, we solve numerically the set of master equations of occupancy probabilities for all atomic sites:

$$\frac{\partial c_A}{\partial t} = \sum_{in=1}^{12} (c_B(i)c_A(in)\Gamma_{AB}(A(in) \longleftrightarrow B(i)) - c_A(i)c_B(in)\Gamma_{AB}(A(i) \longleftrightarrow B(in))). \quad (2)$$

The main difference between the KMF (or the SKMF) approach and the linear Onsager approach is that jump/exchange

FIG. 1. Basic and mixed morphologies obtained at the same temperature ($E_{mix}/k_B T = 2$) but with different flux compositions and various initial conditions: a - rods ($C = 0.3$, initial pattern - spots), b - lamellae ($C = 0.4$, initial pattern - lamellae), c - zigzags ($C = 0.5$, initial pattern - lamellae), d - labyrinth ($C = 0.5$, initial state - random alloy), e - mixed (“two-phase”) morphology “rods plus labyrinth” ($C = 0.4$, initial state - random alloy). Morphologies b,c,d are treated as the same “morphological phase” in this paper.

frequencies Γ_{AB} in the master equations are determined by the interaction energies of the exchanging atoms,

$$\Gamma_{AB}(A(i) \longleftrightarrow B(in)) = v_0 \exp\left(-\frac{E^{saddle} - (E_A(i) + E_B(in))}{k_B T(i)}\right) + \delta\Gamma_{noise}, \quad (3)$$

which in its turn depend on the mentioned occupancies:

$$E_A(i) = \sum_{in=1}^{12} (C_A(in')V_{AA} + C_B(in')V_{AB}). \quad (4)$$

The eq. 2 was solved using the finite-difference scheme. The nondimensional time step $v_0 \cdot dt$ was fixed to 10^{-4} , which assures the stability of the numerical scheme. Typical patterns obtained by SKMF modeling of co-deposition, are shown in the bottom part of Fig. 1. They demonstrate the influence of composition and, sometimes, initial conditions on the morphology in asymptotic steady-state.

To quantify the morphology of the simulated microstructure, we introduce the first parameter P_1 (asymmetry parameter) as a maximum (over all possible rotation angles φ of the Cartesian coordinate axes X', Y' , $x = x' \cos \varphi + y' \sin \varphi$, $y = -x' \sin \varphi + y' \cos \varphi$) of asymmetry along two principal directions:

$$P_1 = \max \left| \frac{\langle (\frac{\partial C}{\partial x'})^2 \rangle - \langle (\frac{\partial C}{\partial y'})^2 \rangle}{\langle (\frac{\partial C}{\partial x'})^2 \rangle + \langle (\frac{\partial C}{\partial y'})^2 \rangle} \right|, \quad (5)$$

$$P_1 = \max \left| \frac{\langle (\frac{\partial C}{\partial x})^2 \rangle - \langle (\frac{\partial C}{\partial y})^2 \rangle \cos 2\varphi + 2 \frac{\partial C}{\partial x} \frac{\partial C}{\partial y} \sin 2\varphi}{\langle (\frac{\partial C}{\partial x})^2 \rangle + \langle (\frac{\partial C}{\partial y})^2 \rangle} \right|. \quad (6)$$

Obviously, in ideal lamellar morphology of any fixed direction it gives 1 and in case of ideal rod morphology it gives 0.

We tried to introduce some alternative morphological parameters based on the correlation function defined for each deposited atomic plane k^{17} :

$$f(k, \Delta i, \Delta j) = \frac{\sum_i^{N_x} \sum_j^{N_y} C(i, j, k) C(i + \Delta i, j + \Delta j, k)}{\sum_i^{N_x} \sum_j^{N_y} C(i, j, k)^2} - 1. \quad (7)$$

Yet, we found that corresponding “alternative” parameters behave very similarly to parameter P_1 but appeared to be less sensitive to morphology than P_1 . In the case of compositions C from about 0.1 to about 0.4 parameter P_1 helps to distinguish the different morphologies for the fractions of minority atoms from about 0.1 to 0.35 - 0.40. For alloys, closer to equiatomic compositions, P_1 may give very similar values for rod-like and labyrinth morphologies. Therefore, we need at least one more parameter, besides P_1 , to distinguish these two morphologies.

This new parameter will be related to the size dependence of the number of minority clusters. Let $L_{max} \cdot L_{max}$ be the total square area of co-deposition. Let $h \cdot h$ ($h < L_{max}$) be the arbitrary sub-region. The number of clusters of the minority phase in the sub-region is noted $N(h)$. Elementary analysis shows that if h is larger than the characteristic length λ (say, period of lamellar structure or the mean distance between neighboring rod centers), for the regular structure N is:

$$1. \text{ Lamellae: } N_{lam} = \frac{h}{\lambda} \implies \ln(N_{lam}) = \ln(h) + const$$

$$2. \text{ Rods: } N_{rod} \approx \frac{h^2}{\lambda^2} \implies \ln(N_{rod}) = 2 \cdot \ln(h) + const$$

Let us introduce $P_2 = \frac{d \ln(N(h))}{d \ln(h)}$. Then, P_2 will be close to 2 for rods, 1 for lamellae, and between about 1 and about 1.5 for

FIG. 2. Four morphologies - rod-like, labyrinth, zigzag, lamellar, and corresponding plots $\ln(N_{clusters})$ versus $\ln(h)$. For each h the average number of clusters is calculated for various positions of squares $h \cdot h$ within the simulation box.

labyrinth. Thus, now we have the following criteria for three basic morphologies:

1. Rod-like: P_1 - low, P_2 - high (close to 2).
2. Labyrinth: P_1 - low, P_2 - medium or low.
3. Lamellar and zigzag: P_1 - high, P_2 - low (close to 1).

These four different cases are depicted in Fig. 2, where the typical images of lamellar, rod-like, and labyrinth structures with corresponding dependencies $\ln(N_{clusters})$ versus $\ln(h)$ is shown.

Now consider the morphological evolution during co-deposition for three kinds of initial patterns: (1) a random mixture of atoms at the first atomic plane, (2) regular individual spots, and (3) periodically situated parallel lamellae. We observe the following asymptotic possibilities:

Random alloy, depending on the composition of the deposition flux and on deposition rate, may asymptotically transform into rod-like or labyrinth morphology, but never reaches lamellar structure with more or less parallel and smooth lamellae. The rod-like initial structure may remain rod-like or it can transform into labyrinth-like, sometimes into zigzags, but it never transforms into a “pure” lamellar structure. Lamellae may transform into rods or may stay unchanged for a rather long time, but eventually, they tend to transform into zigzags or labyrinths or into “superposition” of the labyrinth and rod-like morphology.

At first, we studied the asymptotic morphologies obtained starting from the random substrate and under different compositions of deposited minority component, from $C = 0.1$ to 0.5 (composition step was $dC = 0.01$) and with inverse deposition rate characterized by number M of time steps per atomic plane from $5 \cdot 10^4$ to $2 \cdot 10^6$ (high and low deposition rate).

At all mentioned deposition rates, and concentrations from 0.1 to 0.38 , the initial random alloy at the first (initial) atomic layer leads to a pure rod-like structure. For concentrations C from 0.45 to 0.50 , the asymptotic structure was a labyrinth or zigzags without rods. In the concentration range from $C = 0.39$ to $C = 0.44$, the initial random layer asymptotically transforms into the combined morphology “rods plus labyrinth” with various fractions of rods - Fig. 3.

FIG. 3. Morphological map for steady-state morphology obtained from initial random alloy at the first atomic layer. $E_{mix}/k_B T = 2$, $V_{dep} = \frac{\delta v_0}{M} \frac{1}{v_0 dt}$, $5 \cdot 10^4 < M < 2 \cdot 10^6$.

We specially studied the “two-phase” (mixed) morphologies obtained (at different deposition rates) for compositions of the deposition flux in the range $0.39 \leq C \leq 0.44$ (Fig. 4).

Now we vary the initial conditions and check if the asymptotic topology becomes ambiguous and keeps some memory of the initial pattern when the flux composition belongs to “two-phase” region. In Fig. 5a we show some examples for $C = 0.41$. We found that indeed, the different initial morphologies (lamellar, rod-like, and random) at compositions from the “two-phase” region at the morphology map, lead to different asymptotic patterns. An especially vivid example of memory keeping was obtained for the composition 0.4 of the deposition flux (Fig. 5b): initial random alloy leads to “two-phase” morphology, honeycomb morphology remains almost honeycomb, and lamellar morphology remains lamellar even after 600 deposited atomic planes.

In this work we show that morphology of the two-phase alloy obtained by co-deposition from the vapor phase has a memory of initial conditions at the substrate (besides the conditions of the deposition itself). This memory effect should be especially vivid for some “two-phase” region of mixed morphologies. Note that possibility of morphological hysteresis in directional eutectic crystallization was found in³⁰.

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DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

Data available on request from the authors.

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FIG. 4. “Two-phase” (rods plus labyrinth) asymptotic morphologies obtained from initially random substrates for the deposition flux compositions from about 0.39 to about 0.44 and number M of timesteps from $5 \cdot 10^4$ to $2 \cdot 10^6$ (left). All “two-phase” patterns are characterized by low P_1 (because initial random alloy may give only rods or labyrinths but not lamellae or zigzags). Parameter P_2 systematically decreases from the left to the right boundary of the “two-phase” region (right).

FIG. 5. Examples of memory effect in KMF simulations: (a) Different asymptotic steady-state morphologies for the same flux composition and deposition rate but different initial conditions (at $C = 0.41$ and $M = 50000$ timesteps of 2D-diffusion per one deposited layer); (b) “Ideal” memory effect for $C = 0.40$ - initial random alloy leads to mixed morphology (rods and labyrinth), but initial spots remain spots, and initial lamellae are reconstructed but remain lamellae after 600 deposited atomic layers.

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